

EVALUATING COMPUTER PROGRAMMING COMPETENCE OF SELECTED GRADE 9 STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY

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Evaluating Computer Programming Competence of Selected Grade 9 Students: A Case Study

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Abstract

The Philippine education system is strongly geared toward technological advancement in this era of the Industrial Revolution (IR 4.0). This study aims to evaluate the computer programming competence of selected grade 9 students of Philippine Science High School (PSHS), Cagayan Valley Campus, and identify their learning experiences and challenges for learning strategy. This study used a qualitative method using exploratory study. A semi-structured interview was used to determine the programming learning experience and challenges of the students. Purposive sampling was used with 29 grade 9 students. The main finding of this study is that PSHS students are competent when it comes to their level of computer programming competency. Based on their learning experiences, computer programming subject helps to improve their critical thinking skills, which serve as a tool to solve real-world problems and allows them to learn different programming languages. In addition, they learned the value of patience and improved creativity. Moreover, there were identified challenges when it comes to more technical aspects of programming, such as improper coding syntax, incorrect solutions to problems, and difficulty in debugging. Overall, students' computer programming competence is good but needs further enrichment to hurdle some technical challenges. The results of the study provide useful information for computer science teachers to improve teaching strategies and approaches further. This study provides additional knowledge to the existing literature on computer programming in the K to 12 curricula of the Philippines education system.

Keywords: *computer learning strategies, computer programming, student computer competence*

Introduction

The training of future professionals is very much evident in the high school K to 12 curricula, but the question is how prepared Filipino high school students are for the future. Do they acquire the essential technological competencies expected from them? Recently, activities that include computing have become universal in the classroom setting, whether it is integrated in the subject that serves as a tool to make the teaching and learning processes effective and efficient with the use of technology. The emergence of Information Technology (IT) has drastically improved students' academic performance, given the several benefits of IT. The utilization of IT became more evident and essential to education delivery when the COVID-19 pandemic struck.

Technology and software play an increasing role in almost all areas of society, as well as every aspect of life with the rapid development of digitalization. It is essential to gain a better understanding of its workings as well as what opportunities and risks this entails. As a result, more and more countries have started in the process of starting to introduce Computer Science (CS) into their school curricula. Some countries, such as Finland and Sweden have taken an interdisciplinary approach, and England have introduced CS as a subject of its own, building on the concept of digital competence (Skolverket, 2017). Innovative technologies and practices are implemented in teaching and learning as well. Many countries, such as the United Kingdom, United States and Greece, have introduced a new initiative in their curricula, replacing existing ICT courses with computer and computational science, where students are gradually learning how to program and engage in computational thinking (Psycharis, 2016).

The introduction to computer programming is becoming increasingly popular among students, especially to high school students. Students' curiosity and interest in learning how to utilize new technology is high. The teaching of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) includes computer coding that involves writing, modifying, and putting into practice computer code while exposing students to computational thinking (Grover & Pea, 2013). However, simply teaching students to code does not guarantee that they can apply the knowledge and abilities they have acquired in computer programming to different contexts and circumstances; rather, certain strategies and approaches how to learn the processes need to be created to support technology transfer, especially when it comes to the computer programming (Grover & Pea, 2018). Programming is one of the highly sought-after skills in both the present and future labor markets. The global economy is fast-changing, where robots are replacing more and more workers, and artificial intelligence (AI) is the instantaneous source of knowledge and information. In order to adapt to the fast-changing landscape of our modern world, the basic education must train students with relevant skills in digital fields like programming, AI, machine learning, data science, data analytics, cloud computing, and cybersecurity (Kim & Lee, 2016).

Learning computer programming is not that easy for many students, but it has tremendous role and useful in developing students' technological talents and skills (Sima & Parumal, 2019). Introducing programming in schools can provide a better understanding of basic and essential concepts of coding in solving typical issues and for the purpose of reusability. Programming languages such as C, C++, Python, Ruby, Java, and other platforms were used to create programs or applications that make programmers' work efficient, effective, and faster. Babas (2020) projected that the Philippines would be one of the next ICT hubs and the best breeding ground for ICT professionals in Asia with the help of an ICT-equipped workforce for the advancement and progress of ICT.

The Philippine Science High School (PSHS) Systems offers Computer Science (CS) subjects with advanced Programming Languages such as Python (CS1), C++ (CS2), JavaScript - HTML and CSS (CS3), and Java (CS4). These are the most widely used programming languages today, both in industry and education. The goal of the subject is to facilitate students learning about STEM fields to become future-ready. Some researches show that with the aid of programming, it helps to improve students' learning experiences to strengthen their abilities and thinking skills. The PSHS Computer Science Curriculum aims to develop students to become proficient in technological problem-solving by grounding them in the use of Information and Communications Technology in everyday life and in computational thinking; develop program logic formulation skills through pseudo-coding, flowcharting, and procedural or structured programming using a programming language; teaches the students to understand abstract and theoretical analysis; cultivate student collaboration, innovation, and a sense of community and responsibility; prepare the student to analyze problems needed for the ever-changing modern world; train and develop the student to find solutions using computers for real-life applications; help students learn modularization (work independently to achieve a greater task); and prepares students for careers in Science and Technology. After analyzing the CS1 to CS4 curriculum, the following common content/topic was identified: (a) Programming Basics - Data Types, Constants, Variables, Input, Output, Operations, and Precedence Rules (b) Logical Control Structures -Control Statement and Loops (c) Arrays - Declaration, Initialization, Referencing, Traversing and Practical Applications (d) Functions - Declaring and calling functions.

The current study aims to evaluate the students' competence on computer programming and propose relevant strategies and approaches to improve student knowledge and skills.

Research Questions

There were studies on assessing the programming competencies of students. However, the majority of the studies are focused on IT students and were not in context on high school students who take computer programming subjects. Hence, this study evaluates the computer programming competence of high school students, understands their learning experiences, and identifies their challenges in learning programming which can be used as a basis to enrich teaching and learning strategies and approaches. This study specifically answered the following questions:

1. What is level the of computer programming competence of the Grade 9 students?
2. What are the learning experiences of students in computer programming?
3. What are the challenges of students in learning computer programming?

Literature Review

Computational Thinking

In programming, one of the skills that students need to learn is computational thinking skill. This kind of skill could use by the student to learn the process of breaking down a problem into simple components which promotes not just computational skill but also analytical and critical thinking skills of the students to solve complex real-world problems (Lai, 2021). Technology, has recently been progressively utilized in various fields and industries, such as the social, health, economics, environmental sectors and most especially in education sector, from basic to higher education. Teachers' teaching strategies have been greatly changed by the use of computer and multimedia technologies inside and outside the classroom setting (Rebuta et al., 2022).

Computer Programming in Education

Computer programming is the skill of creating programs that may be used by a variety of devices, such as operating systems, the internet, electronic devices, computer-aided devices, or a mix of these technologies. Students in computer programming, acquire the necessary skills in order to perform well in various IT sectors and industries (Ibezim & Chibuogwu, 2016). In a study by Sima and Parumal (2019), they noted that one of the cornerstones of information technology education is the teaching of computer programming. Rapid advancements in technology help to promote students' creativity, analytical and critical thinking skills, and problem-solving skills, especially in computer programming subject. Computational thinking is acquired through programming; hence learning to program a computer can ultimately help the student to develop computational thinking abilities (Scherer et al., 2020). Computer programming enables users to communicate with computers and other computerized devices, utilize computing in all aspects of human effort, automate processes, and build intelligent machines.

Computer Programming in Schools

Programmers, as stated by Mingoc and Sala (2019), earn the most money in the Philippines. Students who want to study computer programming must complete challenging laboratory tasks in order to learn more and acquire relevant skills before entering to the world of work. Higher-level programming applications such as binary numbers, syntaxes, algorithms, logic circuits, data structures, system analysis and design, and other knowledge of the subject are all important aspects in learning how to code. Programming knowledge should be built continuously and students must apply acquired knowledge and skills. If a student fails to grasp important concepts, that will create more challenging scenario to catch up, and usually, the pace of the teaching in some cases is often driven by the written curriculum and not by how students and teachers create meaningful learning experiences. To address this issue, good facilities and

infrastructure like computer laboratories and other teaching and learning resources must be well provided.

Learning Experience in Computer Programming

Filipino students studying Information Technology in the Northern Philippines show a very high level of programming competency which may be attributed to peer learning, self-learning, research, and good access to internet. Some studies on programming competencies are mostly focused on IT college students while high school students whose schools offer programming curricula have limited studies on students' competence on computer programming. Gathering relevant information on high school students programming competence, the Computer Science teachers could examine and propose relevant strategies and approaches to improve the delivery of the lessons and help to improve student knowledge and skills (Babas, 2020). According to Scherer et al. (2020), it is anticipated that learning programming through game design, robotics, and visual designs rather than text-based languages can be more effective as compared to other techniques. Motivating and encouraging students to practice programming is crucial nowadays. It can be difficult to inspire students and get each of them involved in a work that relies on their sense of importance and confidence in their ability to succeed. In order for students' problem-solving skills to genuinely grow, they must adopt an active rather than passive behavior to complete exercises on their own and create their own plans (Tavares et al., 2022).

Computer Programming Challenges

In learning programming, as cited by Sima and Parumal (2019), teachers spend more time in lectures which makes programming difficult and boring for the students. In lectures, students are often passive because there is a limited mechanism to ensure that they are actually engaged. For computer science education, concepts are focused on problem-solving, and the method of lecturing may not be suitable in this context. The practical application of concepts is crucial that the learning experiences of students must be relevant, and an appropriate teaching strategy is imperative. This is supported by Scherer et al. (2020) where instructional teaching practices should not be confined to a particular approach but rather teachers should offer students a variety of learning experiences and teaching methods. In light of this, teachers must systematically examine the efficacy of various instructional approaches and conditions to address students' challenges, like creating interventions, tools, and features that make computer programming accessible to students (Khan, et. al 2020).

Learning to program involves overcoming a number of challenges for inexperienced programmers. They may encounter issues with a syntax that offers operations that are extremely similar to other operations. Normally they tackle programming by writing code line by line as opposed to employing purposeful, structured programs (Abdul Rahman et al., 2018). One of the main causes of inefficient programming instruction by instructors is their incapacity to observe the challenges of learning to program from the perspective of a new programmer. The learners' comprehension of the programming language will be impacted if there are insufficient effective teaching strategies and instructional resources done by the instructor (Xinogalos, 2016). Debugging is also a difficult skill for inexperienced programmers, since they lack program understanding abilities. Occasionally, inexperienced programmers introduce accidental errors into the source code in the process of debugging.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used qualitative research method using exploratory case study analysis which determines the students' level of programming competence in computer science.

Participants

The participants of the study are selected Grade 9 students of Philippine Science High School – Cagayan Valley Campus, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. According to Creswell and Creswell (2018) some researchers estimate that between 10 and 50 participants are sufficient depending on your type of research and research question. The sampling technique used in this study was non-probability purposive sampling with 29 participants.

Instruments

A semi-structured interview was used to identify learning experiences and the challenges of students in learning the subject.

Procedure

Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data by studying the themes within the gathered dataset to identify meaning for coding. Based from the common topics of CS1 to CS4 (Programming Basics, Logical Control Structures, Arrays and Functions), the desired learning competencies for programming were identified in which the students assessed their competency level if they were a beginner, competent, proficient and expert through a survey.

Ethical Considerations

A semi-structured interview was conducted to identify learning experiences and the challenges of students in learning computer programming. The request to conduct this study was submitted to the Campus Director of the Philippine Science High School –

Cagayan Valley Campus. This study follows the process of seeking consent from the school, parents, and student participants. During the data gathering, protocols and guidelines of getting information from minors were given great consideration. The gathered data were kept for confidentiality and in accordance to the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Results and Discussion

Level of Computer Programming Competence of Students

Programming Basics

The programming basics is the key foundation of learning any programming language. It is the practical skill of designing and creating computer programs that is intended to solve real world problems. It includes declaring correct data type, constant, and variables including the implementation of input, output, operations, and precedence rules.

Figure 1. *Level of programming competence for Programming Basics*

The results show that the majority of the participants have competent basic programming skills which means that they are capable of using and implementing variable declaration, precedence rule, input or output, math expressions and debugging. Some of the participants have proficient competence which implies that they are skillful in doing basic programming. According to Chandra (2022) it is important that students have a good skill in declaring variables to store different data types and perform any operation or task in a program. When it comes to debugging Yen et al. (2012) presented that programming beginners have less developed logical thinking skills it is then important that debugging skills must be reinforced with good programming practice in particular to logic debugging.

Logical Control Structures

Logical Control Structures is defined as a flow of control in codes using algorithm and logic. It helps to analyze and choose which direction of a program flow based on the given argument and conditions. There are three basic types of logic which is known as sequence (follows a sequential flow which depends on the series of instructions), selection (involves a number of conditions or parameters) and iteration (employs a loop which involves a repeat statement).

Figure 2. *Level of programming competence for Logical Control Structures*

For logical control structure, most of the participants have competent to proficient skill in creating logic, branching statements, and

algorithms for creating loop statements. One factor that may contribute to the capable skills of the students in logical control structure is the number of weeks (usually two to three weeks) given for the lesson discussion, simulation and practice. In a study Collier and Downing (2019) their findings suggest that students may mistake a sequential if for an else-if statement, which may cause them to misinterpret a conditional control structure. This may also be a factor why students assessed themselves for having competent skills in logic. In the 2018 study of Bouchard on Learning how to code for loops through play, he encourages educators to adapt and use games to make loop coding more enjoyable for students and improve computer science teacher's pedagogy on active learning.

Array

In programming, an array is a set of data that is stored in a memory location. It is a helpful programming concept for locating and identifying stored elements and value. In the PSHS Computer Science curriculum it is a competency that enables students to declare, initialize, reference, and traverse array elements for practical use.

Figure 3. Level of programming competence for Arrays

A large number of students have competent skills in programming Array. While, several students have beginner skills in representing data arrays, identifying correct arrays for the program, defining and creating arrays, and manipulating arrays using sort and search algorithms. This result may be attributed to the online class modality during the school year 2021-2022 wherein their foundation skills in array should be honed during their C++ programming in grade 8. But unfortunately, some students were not able to fully grasp the concept of array. Based on Priest and Harper (2015) it is important that students need to master the use of array because it can help answer real world problems with a large collection of similar variables to a more simplified code. This is supported by Pearce (2017) where the study said that the use of array makes code easier and a variety of crucial algorithms for sorting, traversing and searching is used.

Functions

Functions are block of code that can be used multiple times. It enables programmers to chunk or decompose a problem into smaller manageable code in order to perform a particular task. Function is an important aspect programming because it makes the code easier to read and reduce the lines of program for faster code run.

Figure 4. Level of programming competence for Functions

Results have shown that most of the students have competent skill in using functions. Some have proficient skills in identifying functions, methods and parameters, use predefined functions, and process/handle function output with or without returned value. Based on the observation of the researcher on the student's performance on implementing functions in JavaScript coding, most of the students were able to solve a problem using function in the class. Functions are very important for programming according to Abdugafforovna (2023), it allows the process of creating code much easier. To improve the quality of work and productivity in coding, it's important to spend a little time understanding the program and thoroughly examine functions. With functions or modules, it allows students to reuse code instead of rewriting it, keep variable namespace clean, and test small parts of a program in isolation from the rest which can be useful in programming languages such as C, Java, Python, etc. (Germain, n.d.).

Learning Experiences of Students in Computer Programming Course

Figure 5. Learning experiences of students in computer programming

Learning experience according to Kolb (1984) is defined as a learning process where knowledge results from the combination of grasping and transforming an experience. In this study, learning experiences is the narrative of students while taking the course. During the semi-structured interview students shared their learning experience while taking the computer programming course.

Learning is fun and exciting. Based on the gathered data on the learning experience of students in computer programming, most of the students said that coding is fun. Further studies described the coding activity in terms of students having fun reported an improvement in their attitudes towards programming and positive change in learning outcomes (Papavlasopoulou et al., 2018). Some of the students said that the subject is fun because they have the freedom to create their own code and the programming is interesting:

I learned that coding is also a fun experience to learn because we can make a website that we prefer. (S3)

My learning in computer science is very fun and exciting. (S4)

It's a very thrilling and fun subject for me really. (S4)

It is a very fun subject but also stressful. Since CS3 is about website programming, I was interested in it and I really paid attention to the classes. (S15)

Teaching patience. Because of the challenging nature of learning how to code it helps the students to be patient. Sosangyo (2022) mentioned that coders can increase the quality of their work and make fewer mistakes, if they have patience and can keep their focus. Patience allows coders to take their time and completely comprehend the problem.

Improving creativity. Coding requires students to dissect problems into their component parts and reassemble them step-by-step and logically. This improves their problem-solving skills and creativity as well (Siegle, 2017). With coding it has allowed the participants to be creative in doing their activities, they mentioned that:

Programming has taught me another way to be creative such as making interactive websites with pleasing aesthetics. (S20)

Computer programming is a very fun subject where I learn to be creative and think outside the box and be more communicative. (S23)

Promoting collaborative coding. In a study by De Jesus and Silveira (2021) on collaborative learning framework, it is important that computer science teachers must use activities that effectively develop Computational Thinking related skills such as student collaborative work with appropriate teacher support. This study is supported by the result of the research that collaboration helps them improve their skills they said that:

When it comes to our assessments, it allowed us to collaborate with our co-scholars and practice skills that we could use in fields that we would eventually pick. (S9)

My learning experiences in computer programming are experiential and collaborative. I prefer learning alongside with other learners

because it helps like you could ask questions with one another and seek for help. (S22)

Developing critical thinking in solving problems. Critical thinking is one of the main aims of programming where it can be improved through real-world approach. With the help of authentic learning this helps the students to answer relevant situation through inquiry. Critical thinking is about resisting the urge to solve problems on autopilot. It is thinking problems thoroughly, systematically and at an inductive method rather than just applying the solution that comes to mind. According to Moraiti et al. (2022), programming skills through play-based approach can help students improve their critical thinking. As narrated by the participants:

I learned to think critically & solve problems by analyzing it thoroughly. (S17)

It taught me how to think in a step-by-step process where it improved my critical thinking. (S20)

Using different programming languages. Learning various programming languages enables students to develop a variety of applications that support people in their daily lives (Ristic and Urosevic, 2016). By utilizing appropriate programming language, it allows students express computational tasks in helpful ways. One student mentioned:

Different programming languages with coding games can hone my problem-solving skills, improve my knowledge of programming concepts, and enjoy the learning process too. (S3)

The said learning experience of the students in programming allows the researcher to have a better understanding of computer science curriculum. It has highlighted the thoughts, skills, and values of the students in learning programming.

STUDENTS CHALLENGES IN COMPUTER PROGRAMMING COURSE

Figure 6. Challenges of students in learning computer programming

Programming has been one of the challenging subjects for computer science students in STEM. The student must have strong critical, analytical, logical, and reasoning skills to program effectively. Based on the result four major challenges were identified namely (1) improper coding syntax (2) incorrect solution to problem (3) difficulty in debugging and (4) learning challenges.

Improper use of coding syntax. Acevedo (2021) defined syntax error as entering an incorrect line of code which prevents the code from running. Based on the results of the study the common syntax errors include incorrect declaration of variables and code; typographical errors such as misspelled code and missing punctuations; incorrect logic for control statements; and lengthy codes which hinders faster runtime. In a study by Alzahrani and Vahid (2021) on common logic errors for programming learners, frequent error that students quickly see and correct is not necessarily a problem; in fact, some research would say that such spotting and correcting constitute an essential component of the learning process, some of the participants mentioned the struggle of fixing a syntax error:

Difficult to remember the syntax of a Programming Language. (S2)

I have a difficulty memorizing things but I don't necessarily have bad syntax or anything like that. (S16)

You'll need to remember or familiarize the functions of different syntax, especially in JavaScript wherein you'll have to really understand and comprehend the connection of each of those characters. (S24)

Incorrect solution to problem. Results show that students have difficulty in understanding the problem and incorrect use of functions. According to Kwon (2017) students have trouble creating code solution plans that computer could execute properly. To become proficient at designing code solution plans to program function students need instructional support from teachers. Some of the participants narrated the challenges they encounter on solving a coding problem:

I have encountered many challenges, but one is when I give up when I don't know how to solve the problem. (S7)

... lacking when it comes to solving the problems, it's truly the challenge because it's like you have to really start over again in order to code. It's like, you can't make a solution/code unless you really know each function and their uses. (S14)

Sometimes, it is difficult to find a solution to a problem as well as comprehending the problem. It's also difficult to plan out what you want the code to do and implement what I have learned. I sometimes feel lost. (S20)

Difficulty in debugging. Debugging as defined by Microsoft (2023) refers to the process of iteratively running a code in a debugging tool usually a compiler to identify the precise place where a programming error occurred. Based on the study by Bottcher et al. (2016) they found out that the key non-technical qualities that are fundamental base competencies in programming, such the capacity to work systematically, appear to correspond with the debugging abilities of students. This suggests that in order to enhance students' debugging abilities, it is important to cover both the technical and necessary base capabilities of students. Dong (2022) suggested that with more varied instruction, students can consider which debugging techniques can help them solve their current problem more quickly. This method of thinking can improve the mastery of debugging abilities and steadily develop their debugging strategy models, assisting them in moving more quickly into more complex debugging stages. Other factors that contribute to having difficulty in debugging was narrated by some participants:

First of all is debugging. Once you're done, and there is one bothersome error, you're done for and you made your effort done. (S2)

...debugging and finding the errors is the hardest step of all. It consumes a lot of time just to find one single error, especially typographical errors. (S5)

... I'm impatient with my codes and debugging, but it can be fixed with time. (S26)

Learning Challenges. Results show that student learning challenges were also a factor in understanding computer programming. Different aspects were mentioned which is having an uncooperative group member, being impatient and procrastinating. When grouping students, it is a must that teachers provide specific intervention to maximize student interaction and learning (Brame & Biel, 2015). To avoid being impatient and procrastinating in programming James (2017) suggested the following techniques: challenge yourself – students must take on real world problems to solve; divide and conquer - break project into smaller modules; Iterate - reduce lines of code, to make them more readable resulting to good performance; getting unstuck - google the error or the solution; and code review. Narrated challenges of the participants:

As for collaboration, there are some times that my group mates are kind of hard to work with since they are hard to communicate with and some of the ideas, we have clash with each other. (S9)

... there are people who make it more difficult, like in a group work activity and someone doesn't cooperate in the group. (S28)

My patience sometimes limits me and I get mad if my code can't work, and sometimes I don't want to work on my assignments due to procrastination and due to the fact that I'm impatient. (S26)

To address the challenges of students the following learning strategies which is backed up by scientific research can be used: (1) remember that there is no nerd gene - the ability to program is a taught skill that can be developed with practice, (2) use peer instruction – to provide one-to-one mentorship of students, (3) use live coding - instead of using slides, (4) use authentic tasks - identify task that students want to engage in, and (5) don't just code - rather than writing code from scratch, students can be given lines of code they need to solve a problem. This way they can improve their syntax ability, check if their solutions, debug if necessary and be interested to learn better (Brown and Wilson, 2018). Although there are numerous difficulties in learning to code, anyone can do it with enough time and effort.

Conclusion

The PSHS Computer Science Curriculum aims to develop students to become competent in problem-solving through computational thinking. The results have shown that the majority of the Grade 9 students have competent level of competency in computer programming based on the curriculum. This implies that there is a need for competency improvement since the level is lower than proficient and expert. The students' learning experiences in computer programming includes the subject as fun and exciting, teaches patience, improves creativity and critical thinking, and helps students to use different programming languages. However, there is a need to improve on the students' coding syntax, finding the right solution to a problem, debugging, and learning challenges. And in order to address the challenges of the students, there is a need to strengthen and innovate the teachers' teaching methods or strategies in delivering programming lessons.

Based on the nature of exploratory study, as a possible introduction for further research the future researchers may diversify and expand the number of participants to different grade levels in junior high school and include schools that offer computer science. The results of the study are useful in guiding computer science teachers to further improve their teaching strategy implemented in the class. In addition, the research paper provides additional knowledge to the existing literature of computer programming in the Philippines.

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